

Gaia Data Release 3

Ellipsoidal Variables with Possible Black-Hole or Neutron Star secondaries - supplementary material

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1. *Gaia* G-band light curves of our candidates

This section presents folded *Gaia* light curves in the *G* band of the 262 candidates with $\hat{q}_{\min}^{-1\sigma} > 1$, in descending $\hat{q}_{\min}$ order. For each candidate, the *Gaia* DR3 identifier (id), together with the *Gaia* period in days and the value of $\hat{q}_{\min}$, are given, and a three-harmonics model is plotted with a solid red line.

2. Data table of our candidates

Given below a summary table containing results of the analysis performed on our 262 candidates with $\hat{q}_{\min}^{-1\sigma} > 1$, in descending $\hat{q}_{\min}$ order. The table includes the *Gaia* DR3 id, *Gaia* orbital period, reference time T_0 [BJD-2455197.5] which was chosen so that $a_{2s} = 0$, average *G* magnitude $\bar{G}$, and cosine and sine Fourier coefficients a_{ic}, a_{is} $\{i = 1, 2, 3\}$ of the three-harmonic model, defined by equation (1), each with its uncertainty. The table also gives the total number of *G*-band FoV transits, the derived mMMR and the lower-percentile mMMR. Additional details are found in the paper, and the table is online available at the CDS.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5938420387082046976	0.314117 0.000054	2244.03610 0.00056	17.8719 0.0018	0.0098 0.0028	0.1315 0.0036	-0.0026 0.0026	0.0226 0.0033	0.0000 0.0021	-0.0115 0.0035	43	10.0	5.6
2613886138222158464	0.49774 0.00012	2423.3476 0.0020	18.6571 0.0039	-0.0103 0.0047	0.1105 0.0065	0.0229 0.0067	-0.0110 0.0067	0.0000 0.0046	0.0079 0.0057	46	3.4	2.1
4123054392395089920	0.62299 0.00021	2425.4947 0.0013	17.7272 0.0031	-0.0101 0.0023	0.1104 0.0047	-0.0109 0.0029	0.0220 0.0055	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0105 0.0038	43	3.4	2.2
1892965058567426560	0.261008 0.000044	2191.02880 0.00049	17.6875 0.0022	0.0023 0.0033	0.1097 0.0035	0.0008 0.0028	-0.0062 0.0028	0.0000 0.0026	0.0113 0.0033	36	3.3	2.2
4041883019496151424	1.12284 0.00077	2355.7487 0.0054	18.3060 0.0036	-0.0314 0.0057	0.1097 0.0061	0.0003 0.0052	-0.0068 0.0055	0.0000 0.0063	0.0041 0.0054	34	3.3	2.1
4116728150381233280	0.330273 0.000043	2487.1291 0.0014	18.7504 0.0035	0.0175 0.0059	0.1078 0.0074	0.0123 0.0061	-0.0068 0.0061	0.0000 0.0040	0.0032 0.0059	53	3.0	1.9
6038453229081523072	0.327324 0.000082	2105.02175 0.00072	16.5562 0.0020	-0.0002 0.0035	0.1073 0.0042	0.0019 0.0037	-0.0101 0.0033	0.0000 0.0023	0.0057 0.0031	41	2.9	2.0
4516392793079294976	0.316059 0.000046	2159.86061 0.00074	18.9664 0.0019	0.0214 0.0032	0.1066 0.0035	0.0048 0.0029	0.0014 0.0028	0.0000 0.0026	0.0034 0.0033	41	2.9	1.9
4056017172771375616	0.410707 0.000093	2394.25673 0.00078	16.9046 0.0016	-0.0038 0.0023	0.1066 0.0031	-0.0008 0.0024	-0.0049 0.0027	0.0000 0.0024	0.0112 0.0028	44	2.9	1.9
5889592931122816512	0.341463 0.000081	2204.82654 0.00084	18.3464 0.0021	0.0162 0.0031	0.1044 0.0037	-0.0004 0.0030	-0.0033 0.0033	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0129 0.0034	39	2.6	1.8
4068402346632484864	1.27615 0.00079	2356.9575 0.0056	18.0847 0.0044	-0.0103 0.0062	0.1043 0.0070	-0.0132 0.0062	-0.0015 0.0064	0.0000 0.0055	0.0135 0.0061	39	2.6	1.6
4042390512917208960	0.89522 0.00046	2383.8996 0.0014	13.7822 0.0015	0.0000 0.0022	0.1039 0.0022	-0.0074 0.0023	0.0046 0.0020	0.0000 0.0020	0.0012 0.0019	38	2.5	1.8
1833609671396897024	1.20849 0.00074	2202.2576 0.0028	18.1657 0.0028	-0.0286 0.0054	0.1035 0.0048	-0.0215 0.0038	-0.0010 0.0030	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0083 0.0038	53	2.5	1.7
4068544041908031488	0.58456 0.00025	2430.2668 0.0026	18.9518 0.0043	0.0258 0.0063	0.1033 0.0064	0.0116 0.0064	-0.0027 0.0058	0.0000 0.0057	-0.0153 0.0058	43	2.5	1.6
6053386525470178560	0.96892 0.00052	2206.1084 0.0033	19.5447 0.0035	-0.0177 0.0045	0.1032 0.0055	-0.0122 0.0053	0.0016 0.0053	0.0000 0.0042	-0.0040 0.0047	40	2.5	1.6

Table S1: Fitted parameters of the 262 candidates, in descending $\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$ order.

Fig. S1: Folded *Gaia* light curves in the *G* band of the 262 candidates in descending $\hat{q}_{\min}$ order. For each candidate, the *Gaia* DR3 id, together with the *Gaia* period in days and the value of $\hat{q}_{\min}$, are given. The epoch of the second-harmonic minimum corresponds to phases 0 and 0.5, and a three-harmonics model is plotted with a solid red line. All curves are plotted with a mag range of 0.4, for convenience. The residuals are plotted in the lower panels and are shown between -0.1 to 0.1 mag for clarity.

Fig. S1: Continued

Fig. S1: Continued

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
227985355226451712	0.346954 0.000076	2100.87566 0.00066	17.6393 0.0021	-0.0127 0.0036	0.1032 0.0039	0.0012 0.0030	0.0031 0.0028	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0047 0.0035	39	2.5	1.7
4042492733124112640	0.97511 0.00056	2350.6056 0.0042	18.1594 0.0043	-0.0169 0.0062	0.1025 0.0056	-0.0016 0.0046	-0.0144 0.0049	0.0000 0.0054	0.0039 0.0065	34	2.4	1.6
2034263023023544320	1.7873 0.0021	2211.1771 0.0055	18.6164 0.0031	0.0277 0.0040	0.1023 0.0046	0.0105 0.0035	0.0020 0.0048	0.0000 0.0041	-0.0073 0.0055	53	2.4	1.6
4049067258553241216	1.19073 0.00079	2290.2698 0.0047	17.4659 0.0044	0.0133 0.0039	0.1017 0.0064	0.0098 0.0048	-0.0008 0.0085	0.0000 0.0046	0.0025 0.0068	29	2.3	1.5
4383313295810461184	0.259789 0.000035	2185.5570 0.0011	17.9288 0.0038	0.0013 0.0033	0.1017 0.0064	-0.0082 0.0047	0.0234 0.0073	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0067 0.0045	51	2.3	1.5
5985264010492665216	0.264161 0.000047	2103.22994 0.00095	19.3656 0.0032	0.0143 0.0049	0.1011 0.0049	0.0082 0.0045	0.0080 0.0042	0.0000 0.0042	0.0030 0.0045	48	2.2	1.5
5939640634494621440	0.292932 0.000062	2269.33105 0.00082	17.9057 0.0024	-0.0190 0.0041	0.1006 0.0042	-0.0076 0.0033	-0.0082 0.0030	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0005 0.0036	38	2.2	1.5
2186314206807858048	0.273138 0.000054	2214.85392 0.00087	18.4732 0.0029	-0.0184 0.0044	0.1003 0.0050	-0.0018 0.0038	-0.0215 0.0043	0.0000 0.0036	0.0033 0.0045	36	2.2	1.5
1824905460657943936	0.47632 0.00018	2148.1579 0.0016	18.4914 0.0032	-0.0025 0.0043	0.1003 0.0050	-0.0150 0.0040	-0.0057 0.0050	0.0000 0.0042	-0.0030 0.0057	44	2.2	1.5
5990533252504976896	0.92363 0.00049	2164.5275 0.0023	17.6908 0.0023	-0.0280 0.0036	0.0999 0.0036	-0.0110 0.0028	0.0115 0.0027	0.0000 0.0026	0.0049 0.0032	42	2.1	1.5
5942287781774326016	0.59140 0.00021	2134.7088 0.0024	19.1645 0.0035	-0.0153 0.0046	0.0999 0.0054	0.0017 0.0050	-0.0014 0.0054	0.0000 0.0046	-0.0017 0.0046	42	2.1	1.4
4070409432055253760	0.64373 0.00027	2251.7337 0.0013	16.6490 0.0018	-0.0139 0.0026	0.0995 0.0027	0.0015 0.0026	0.0005 0.0025	0.0000 0.0026	0.0045 0.0028	29	2.1	1.5
5887986922603177984	0.48350 0.00013	2177.3829 0.0011	17.5471 0.0021	-0.0124 0.0036	0.0994 0.0031	-0.0036 0.0031	0.0080 0.0023	0.0000 0.0026	0.0037 0.0025	43	2.1	1.5
4123554910705949184	0.46367 0.00014	2410.1052 0.0014	18.1393 0.0026	-0.0161 0.0036	0.0993 0.0042	-0.0048 0.0036	-0.0025 0.0038	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0012 0.0041	43	2.1	1.4
4049863167529174528	1.2326 0.0012	2271.6591 0.0045	17.7074 0.0041	0.0006 0.0043	0.0991 0.0038	-0.0020 0.0041	0.0038 0.0065	0.0000 0.0054	-0.0113 0.0031	29	2.1	1.4

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4321356266589507584	0.302408 0.000060	2129.1235 0.0010	18.0994 0.0033	0.0135 0.0043	0.0990 0.0053	0.0053 0.0044	-0.0045 0.0054	0.0000 0.0043	0.0100 0.0054	40	2.1	1.4
4111472617942868480	0.90575 0.00064	2264.5219 0.0036	17.5415 0.0032	-0.0288 0.0050	0.0990 0.0049	-0.0089 0.0041	-0.0028 0.0043	0.0000 0.0044	0.0043 0.0042	34	2.0	1.4
4133786897189283840	0.323572 0.000083	2232.55965 0.00088	17.4026 0.0022	-0.0050 0.0034	0.0990 0.0038	0.0042 0.0033	-0.0102 0.0032	0.0000 0.0028	0.0029 0.0032	54	2.0	1.4
1811641429068979456	0.294163 0.000054	2208.37283 0.00087	17.1962 0.0026	-0.0113 0.0033	0.0989 0.0046	0.0008 0.0032	-0.0048 0.0046	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0021 0.0047	41	2.0	1.4
4119752632040146816	0.54544 0.00020	2378.5514 0.0024	18.8840 0.0049	0.0298 0.0085	0.0989 0.0071	0.0095 0.0063	-0.0179 0.0047	0.0000 0.0052	-0.0086 0.0060	41	2.0	1.3
5978280432323971200	0.50856 0.00020	2286.5397 0.0020	18.4474 0.0035	-0.0075 0.0056	0.0987 0.0055	-0.0141 0.0047	0.0082 0.0046	0.0000 0.0045	0.0001 0.0066	48	2.0	1.4
6029163558415639936	0.283148 0.000046	2314.48228 0.00073	17.7682 0.0023	-0.0130 0.0035	0.0986 0.0042	-0.0053 0.0035	-0.0082 0.0035	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0008 0.0035	42	2.0	1.4
5929021035796328448	0.266586 0.000050	2209.99661 0.00098	18.6203 0.0035	-0.0222 0.0056	0.0986 0.0058	-0.0063 0.0051	-0.0080 0.0045	0.0000 0.0040	0.0020 0.0048	45	2.0	1.3
3005724873744854400	0.353007 0.000064	2212.0273 0.0010	17.6909 0.0031	-0.0204 0.0052	0.0985 0.0056	-0.0058 0.0061	0.0128 0.0046	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0030 0.0044	31	2.0	1.3
5532108401998093056	0.281160 0.000042	2223.88025 0.00066	17.5074 0.0020	0.0153 0.0028	0.0983 0.0032	-0.0023 0.0030	0.0015 0.0030	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0054 0.0029	41	2.0	1.4
1827765565254918272	0.96806 0.00067	2184.8263 0.0052	19.0914 0.0048	-0.0213 0.0060	0.0981 0.0083	-0.0112 0.0062	0.0066 0.0081	0.0000 0.0057	-0.0160 0.0073	44	2.0	1.2
2072345669060000640	0.373967 0.000079	2232.69385 0.00072	17.6158 0.0017	-0.0141 0.0023	0.0981 0.0030	0.0000 0.0023	0.0006 0.0029	0.0000 0.0023	0.0017 0.0033	43	2.0	1.4
4117344014362469248	1.12572 0.00058	2384.9853 0.0031	17.9077 0.0021	0.0087 0.0026	0.0980 0.0035	0.0048 0.0031	-0.0001 0.0034	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0039 0.0034	42	2.0	1.4
5938370526760023552	0.41678 0.00015	2277.48949 0.00087	17.8870 0.0017	-0.0150 0.0026	0.0980 0.0030	0.0030 0.0032	0.0044 0.0024	0.0000 0.0025	0.0028 0.0024	40	2.0	1.4
4121502844048485120	1.09802 0.00076	2406.0723 0.0019	17.8135 0.0015	-0.0181 0.0023	0.0979 0.0022	-0.0068 0.0021	-0.0032 0.0021	0.0000 0.0021	-0.0029 0.0020	51	2.0	1.4

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4059574436577349632	0.86396 0.00047	2272.2939 0.0027	16.9834 0.0026	0.0063 0.0037	0.0978 0.0046	-0.0011 0.0036	0.0120 0.0042	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0143 0.0043	28	1.9	1.3
2204247280119303808	0.319809 0.000072	2226.6427 0.0011	18.4264 0.0030	0.0174 0.0043	0.0978 0.0047	0.0002 0.0044	-0.0032 0.0039	0.0000 0.0038	-0.0023 0.0043	33	1.9	1.3
4315611283949759872	0.79238 0.00037	2171.7412 0.0027	19.2290 0.0031	-0.0180 0.0043	0.0977 0.0044	-0.0164 0.0044	0.0048 0.0045	0.0000 0.0044	0.0022 0.0044	61	1.9	1.3
5972653127516529024	0.44851 0.00021	2219.8624 0.0011	17.4636 0.0023	0.0080 0.0022	0.0976 0.0034	-0.0138 0.0026	0.0009 0.0041	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0009 0.0031	28	1.9	1.4
4107801593552947584	0.33705 0.00012	2313.25335 0.00080	17.4852 0.0020	-0.0140 0.0027	0.0976 0.0032	0.0039 0.0027	0.0003 0.0030	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0027 0.0030	40	1.9	1.4
4309230779322958080	1.4874 0.0015	2197.3077 0.0060	17.9579 0.0035	0.0184 0.0053	0.0976 0.0052	0.0075 0.0069	-0.0104 0.0046	0.0000 0.0047	0.0014 0.0040	30	1.9	1.3
5889781870980547840	0.339736 0.000083	2122.5855 0.0010	18.4482 0.0027	-0.0217 0.0047	0.0976 0.0042	0.0045 0.0037	0.0010 0.0031	0.0000 0.0032	0.0001 0.0035	44	1.9	1.3
5540344328205082880	0.305709 0.000061	2238.7448 0.0011	19.4390 0.0033	0.0160 0.0046	0.0974 0.0056	0.0082 0.0051	0.0023 0.0050	0.0000 0.0040	0.0019 0.0046	50	1.9	1.3
4361779429301138560	0.321689 0.000049	2338.22731 0.00078	17.9390 0.0026	0.0109 0.0045	0.0974 0.0054	0.0149 0.0042	0.0052 0.0041	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0119 0.0042	46	1.9	1.3
5881690427478435584	0.54635 0.00018	2165.2419 0.0022	18.1461 0.0035	-0.0062 0.0040	0.0974 0.0048	-0.0153 0.0048	-0.0119 0.0054	0.0000 0.0046	0.0019 0.0045	43	1.9	1.3
5934239528450798720	0.338507 0.000082	2173.9736 0.0014	18.7905 0.0035	0.0233 0.0050	0.0974 0.0055	-0.0052 0.0051	0.0041 0.0051	0.0000 0.0046	-0.0044 0.0050	49	1.9	1.3
5970830893156863104	0.95753 0.00065	2268.9040 0.0027	17.4940 0.0024	-0.0378 0.0038	0.0974 0.0040	-0.0105 0.0033	0.0041 0.0032	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0011 0.0037	44	1.9	1.3
2055977827881625984	1.8189 0.0025	2208.2701 0.0054	18.1518 0.0056	0.0086 0.0034	0.0973 0.0086	0.0069 0.0036	0.043 0.011	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0194 0.0056	49	1.9	1.2
5832556693145324800	0.355998 0.000084	2177.88203 0.00083	17.9045 0.0021	-0.0091 0.0026	0.0970 0.0034	-0.0047 0.0029	-0.0024 0.0034	0.0000 0.0025	0.0060 0.0033	46	1.9	1.3
5977824543018395904	1.2407 0.0011	2268.3179 0.0033	17.4311 0.0024	-0.0092 0.0029	0.0967 0.0032	-0.0107 0.0030	0.0051 0.0035	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0023 0.0035	46	1.9	1.3

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5962408672771256960	0.80764 0.00032	2444.4403 0.0036	19.1682 0.0038	0.0086 0.0059	0.0967 0.0056	-0.0161 0.0055	0.0084 0.0049	0.0000 0.0051	0.0066 0.0049	49	1.9	1.3
2018326662796791808	0.259352 0.000044	2157.8739 0.0014	18.2798 0.0041	-0.0207 0.0064	0.0966 0.0072	-0.0011 0.0068	0.0273 0.0062	0.0000 0.0053	-0.0070 0.0057	43	1.8	1.2
5952317629931188864	0.334504 0.000097	2209.82226 0.00063	17.7633 0.0019	-0.0208 0.0033	0.0965 0.0039	-0.0039 0.0035	0.0072 0.0030	0.0000 0.0023	-0.0017 0.0029	43	1.8	1.3
3031142245391867008	0.87796 0.00044	2145.8138 0.0018	17.7199 0.0018	-0.0014 0.0028	0.0965 0.0027	0.0020 0.0027	-0.0001 0.0023	0.0000 0.0023	-0.0076 0.0023	42	1.8	1.3
2062815793766426368	0.86602 0.00039	2231.7284 0.0019	17.8037 0.0020	-0.0091 0.0029	0.0964 0.0031	-0.0040 0.0027	-0.0014 0.0027	0.0000 0.0026	0.0007 0.0029	59	1.8	1.3
4116865658058002176	0.66849 0.00027	2394.2923 0.0028	18.8996 0.0042	0.0264 0.0062	0.0964 0.0061	0.0115 0.0054	-0.0027 0.0050	0.0000 0.0052	0.0109 0.0058	42	1.8	1.2
588797226016445696	0.383677 0.000078	2157.62539 0.00082	17.8236 0.0020	-0.0120 0.0029	0.0963 0.0032	-0.0000 0.0027	0.0049 0.0030	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0040 0.0031	50	1.8	1.3
4059248427022016128	0.95497 0.00057	2326.6792 0.0018	18.3441 0.0018	0.0084 0.0025	0.0963 0.0028	0.0021 0.0023	0.0013 0.0026	0.0000 0.0023	0.0011 0.0027	60	1.8	1.3
4322206498284428032	0.377082 0.000082	2144.2519 0.0015	19.0042 0.0034	0.0197 0.0053	0.0962 0.0053	0.0004 0.0057	-0.0127 0.0049	0.0000 0.0046	-0.0041 0.0058	39	1.8	1.2
6020259988135198080	1.1549 0.0010	2131.7325 0.0036	17.9963 0.0025	0.0243 0.0030	0.0961 0.0037	0.0132 0.0037	-0.0059 0.0041	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0008 0.0033	30	1.8	1.3
4141860374856674816	0.340986 0.000072	2335.1687 0.0012	17.7516 0.0026	-0.0049 0.0039	0.0960 0.0048	-0.0007 0.0037	0.0131 0.0041	0.0000 0.0032	-0.0005 0.0042	47	1.8	1.2
5966221774764182272	0.37291 0.00010	2265.2092 0.0013	18.6073 0.0028	0.0125 0.0041	0.0960 0.0046	-0.0080 0.0046	-0.0008 0.0038	0.0000 0.0037	-0.0006 0.0038	42	1.8	1.2
4117139329111282176	0.76374 0.00041	2417.3261 0.0022	18.9662 0.0027	-0.0108 0.0043	0.0959 0.0037	-0.0057 0.0035	-0.0065 0.0032	0.0000 0.0035	-0.0002 0.0038	41	1.8	1.3
2163883040038422272	0.350006 0.000066	2197.55162 0.00086	17.0853 0.0022	0.0039 0.0029	0.0958 0.0036	0.0003 0.0035	-0.0103 0.0032	0.0000 0.0029	0.0020 0.0031	41	1.8	1.3
4123887787851678208	1.9493 0.0017	2422.9896 0.0069	18.0462 0.0032	0.0269 0.0046	0.0958 0.0045	0.0121 0.0039	-0.0049 0.0040	0.0000 0.0043	-0.0053 0.0046	60	1.8	1.2

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4116599537584168064	0.318284 0.000058	2263.99036 0.00079	18.1669 0.0025	-0.0184 0.0029	0.0957 0.0040	-0.0021 0.0032	-0.0082 0.0042	0.0000 0.0029	0.0006 0.0037	31	1.8	1.3
2067003416937763840	0.47401 0.00015	2225.8240 0.0012	18.9732 0.0024	0.0280 0.0032	0.0957 0.0037	0.0022 0.0031	-0.0200 0.0036	0.0000 0.0031	0.0013 0.0038	42	1.8	1.3
4305618402578226688	0.94493 0.00066	2154.3442 0.0048	19.2713 0.0045	0.0208 0.0058	0.0956 0.0064	-0.0078 0.0059	-0.0042 0.0065	0.0000 0.0058	0.0143 0.0062	33	1.8	1.2
5942832448022292224	0.317324 0.000082	2278.7801 0.0013	18.4988 0.0031	-0.0044 0.0045	0.0956 0.0056	-0.0192 0.0047	-0.0126 0.0046	0.0000 0.0052	0.0006 0.0058	41	1.8	1.2
3121590000331875456	0.39342 0.00010	2255.81446 0.00072	17.0162 0.0014	0.0063 0.0021	0.0954 0.0025	0.0056 0.0024	0.0039 0.0020	0.0000 0.0019	0.0034 0.0021	27	1.8	1.3
5951187813006270336	0.72532 0.00043	2223.4078 0.0023	18.3023 0.0031	-0.0249 0.0040	0.0953 0.0038	-0.0162 0.0045	-0.0058 0.0034	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0035 0.0033	35	1.8	1.2
3421155718593729920	0.52675 0.00022	2329.3188 0.0015	18.4338 0.0025	-0.0071 0.0038	0.0953 0.0036	-0.0007 0.0034	-0.0080 0.0032	0.0000 0.0033	0.0003 0.0034	50	1.7	1.2
3050008735350518656	0.38212 0.00010	2152.5508 0.0014	17.2505 0.0032	-0.0117 0.0039	0.0952 0.0047	-0.0166 0.0050	-0.0091 0.0050	0.0000 0.0043	-0.0058 0.0041	28	1.7	1.2
4070996811788952704	0.86546 0.00060	2276.3766 0.0044	18.6344 0.0044	-0.0068 0.0074	0.0950 0.0071	-0.0022 0.0040	0.0042 0.0058	0.0000 0.0068	-0.0197 0.0060	30	1.7	1.1
5523195971203200128	0.56308 0.00024	2224.4810 0.0026	18.3370 0.0039	-0.0143 0.0061	0.0950 0.0060	-0.0101 0.0056	0.0123 0.0047	0.0000 0.0050	-0.0010 0.0051	41	1.7	1.2
5877724665163917696	0.49266 0.00016	2264.5120 0.0013	18.7859 0.0023	0.0202 0.0031	0.0950 0.0035	0.0010 0.0034	0.0027 0.0034	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0046 0.0036	64	1.7	1.2
5937212607951729152	0.78141 0.00040	2172.2278 0.0017	17.8986 0.0023	-0.0251 0.0034	0.0950 0.0028	-0.0074 0.0023	0.0117 0.0025	0.0000 0.0029	0.0010 0.0033	47	1.7	1.2
5968236805936092032	0.73218 0.00047	2235.3131 0.0025	18.9345 0.0027	0.0112 0.0042	0.0950 0.0038	0.0122 0.0038	0.0018 0.0035	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0039 0.0038	42	1.7	1.2
6018703358859640704	0.77763 0.00053	2188.8142 0.0025	17.5937 0.0029	-0.0018 0.0054	0.0949 0.0047	-0.0007 0.0033	-0.0036 0.0027	0.0000 0.0027	-0.0115 0.0033	30	1.7	1.2
4090022898467521920	0.70299 0.00040	2212.5637 0.0013	17.1720 0.0017	-0.0108 0.0024	0.0949 0.0022	-0.0094 0.0024	0.0013 0.0021	0.0000 0.0023	0.0009 0.0021	26	1.7	1.2

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4043323684736161408	0.89117 0.00044	2378.6109 0.0033	17.6395 0.0036	-0.0179 0.0047	0.0949 0.0054	-0.0118 0.0048	-0.0095 0.0052	0.0000 0.0045	0.0095 0.0049	38	1.7	1.2
4064671222613038720	0.69855 0.00032	2232.4215 0.0020	17.5815 0.0023	-0.0151 0.0036	0.0949 0.0037	-0.0051 0.0037	0.0107 0.0031	0.0000 0.0029	0.0027 0.0030	30	1.7	1.2
4117842745932000640	0.66775 0.00040	2306.3396 0.0022	18.3247 0.0036	0.0242 0.0059	0.0949 0.0051	0.0091 0.0041	-0.0011 0.0038	0.0000 0.0043	-0.0089 0.0042	32	1.7	1.2
2060076223135895936	0.366397 0.000071	2230.65053 0.00089	17.3734 0.0029	-0.0159 0.0056	0.0949 0.0056	-0.0140 0.0042	0.0019 0.0032	0.0000 0.0031	0.0057 0.0037	42	1.7	1.2
4118450363567306752	0.81241 0.00034	2400.4801 0.0024	17.6543 0.0025	0.0169 0.0038	0.0948 0.0041	0.0053 0.0035	0.0001 0.0034	0.0000 0.0032	0.0050 0.0038	38	1.7	1.2
4110445059963339264	0.97208 0.00070	2286.6140 0.0027	18.1807 0.0024	-0.0210 0.0032	0.0947 0.0033	-0.0073 0.0033	0.0067 0.0036	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0028 0.0033	31	1.7	1.2
4119897664546481280	0.86212 0.00047	2359.3597 0.0017	17.5097 0.0017	0.0263 0.0024	0.0946 0.0025	0.0172 0.0021	-0.0032 0.0023	0.0000 0.0021	0.0021 0.0025	45	1.7	1.2
5893822099469992320	0.79146 0.00037	2134.1653 0.0029	18.5093 0.0037	0.0105 0.0046	0.0946 0.0053	0.0117 0.0049	-0.0090 0.0057	0.0000 0.0047	0.0117 0.0048	46	1.7	1.2
1809102278764951808	0.285391 0.000055	2238.62702 0.00070	17.6638 0.0021	-0.0031 0.0028	0.0946 0.0030	-0.0071 0.0030	0.0057 0.0030	0.0000 0.0027	0.0054 0.0027	39	1.7	1.2
259820095204356608	0.316389 0.000059	2161.7573 0.0010	18.1503 0.0025	-0.0046 0.0040	0.0945 0.0045	-0.0028 0.0034	0.0117 0.0034	0.0000 0.0030	-0.0054 0.0042	50	1.7	1.2
445067811414955904	0.78164 0.00040	2135.0702 0.0023	18.6849 0.0026	0.0055 0.0038	0.0944 0.0036	0.0034 0.0034	-0.0135 0.0034	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0046 0.0037	44	1.7	1.2
4318036463047098240	0.314137 0.000058	2119.4720 0.0012	17.4927 0.0033	-0.0118 0.0049	0.0944 0.0066	0.0060 0.0046	-0.0126 0.0051	0.0000 0.0035	-0.0045 0.0054	37	1.7	1.1
5938292323993830016	0.313719 0.000043	2231.3130 0.0012	18.2603 0.0035	0.0204 0.0052	0.0944 0.0052	0.0063 0.0046	-0.0108 0.0046	0.0000 0.0045	0.0045 0.0049	44	1.7	1.2
4316136502611146624	0.89639 0.00054	2066.2940 0.0030	18.6573 0.0030	0.0091 0.0045	0.0943 0.0038	0.0135 0.0040	0.0019 0.0037	0.0000 0.0040	-0.0076 0.0036	43	1.7	1.2
4175329057832249216	1.3760 0.0012	2291.8575 0.0077	18.3220 0.0047	-0.0018 0.0083	0.0943 0.0078	-0.0242 0.0063	-0.0090 0.0056	0.0000 0.0053	0.0097 0.0071	37	1.7	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5942571073496125568	0.47218 0.00013	2164.5233 0.0011	18.3159 0.0023	-0.0105 0.0037	0.0942 0.0031	-0.0126 0.0032	-0.0010 0.0026	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0031 0.0026	51	1.7	1.2
4321379974809694848	0.92030 0.00049	2158.7781 0.0019	17.0847 0.0019	0.0159 0.0026	0.0942 0.0030	-0.0035 0.0025	0.0008 0.0027	0.0000 0.0023	0.0032 0.0028	44	1.7	1.2
2071059412252600576	0.49199 0.00021	2215.9317 0.0015	18.5184 0.0025	-0.0010 0.0033	0.0942 0.0038	-0.0052 0.0028	0.0139 0.0037	0.0000 0.0035	-0.0070 0.0046	43	1.7	1.2
4096153603465854720	0.86104 0.00050	2295.8124 0.0025	18.2049 0.0030	0.0240 0.0049	0.0942 0.0058	0.0060 0.0045	-0.0006 0.0046	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0006 0.0051	28	1.7	1.1
1968171924489519488	0.271390 0.000047	2234.08416 0.00060	18.4071 0.0019	0.0358 0.0024	0.0942 0.0026	-0.0002 0.0024	0.0057 0.0028	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0037 0.0028	50	1.7	1.2
4123837592644301056	0.343691 0.000076	2435.8365 0.0011	18.7705 0.0035	0.0174 0.0044	0.0941 0.0060	-0.0033 0.0053	-0.0113 0.0059	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0022 0.0048	41	1.7	1.1
4513206129189260032	0.64550 0.00027	2124.7746 0.0016	18.2330 0.0023	-0.0130 0.0036	0.0941 0.0033	-0.0099 0.0030	-0.0013 0.0026	0.0000 0.0027	-0.0024 0.0030	44	1.7	1.2
4068536693229974912	0.61348 0.00026	2442.5391 0.0021	18.5218 0.0029	-0.0152 0.0037	0.0941 0.0040	-0.0062 0.0039	0.0056 0.0044	0.0000 0.0040	-0.0037 0.0042	35	1.7	1.2
4318085391317069568	0.42491 0.00013	2138.3304 0.0013	17.6525 0.0029	-0.0242 0.0043	0.0939 0.0039	-0.0103 0.0038	-0.0050 0.0036	0.0000 0.0038	-0.0032 0.0037	41	1.7	1.2
5836122100162716544	0.259831 0.000043	2194.38785 0.00054	18.3152 0.0017	-0.0049 0.0025	0.0938 0.0024	-0.0050 0.0023	0.0084 0.0023	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0000 0.0025	57	1.6	1.2
4479262835157176448	0.313370 0.000058	2282.98742 0.00065	17.1939 0.0018	0.0086 0.0025	0.0938 0.0034	0.0075 0.0029	0.0022 0.0031	0.0000 0.0022	0.0030 0.0028	46	1.6	1.2
5935151607712641152	0.387107 0.000096	2212.37008 0.00063	17.6373 0.0016	0.0154 0.0024	0.0938 0.0026	-0.0030 0.0028	-0.0031 0.0022	0.0000 0.0019	-0.0035 0.0019	44	1.6	1.2
5320709733731310720	0.272833 0.000059	2187.16830 0.00082	18.3314 0.0025	-0.0120 0.0036	0.0938 0.0036	-0.0019 0.0032	0.0148 0.0034	0.0000 0.0037	-0.0040 0.0038	37	1.6	1.2
5826920940137873792	0.293029 0.000060	2231.9881 0.0010	18.8723 0.0031	-0.0213 0.0044	0.0938 0.0045	-0.0088 0.0041	0.0019 0.0043	0.0000 0.0041	-0.0009 0.0046	49	1.6	1.1
4123238874157017984	0.346428 0.000083	2429.8785 0.0013	19.0220 0.0036	-0.0093 0.0049	0.0938 0.0058	0.0046 0.0057	0.0168 0.0056	0.0000 0.0045	-0.0100 0.0049	40	1.6	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4064707987597656576	0.71082 0.00044	2253.5672 0.0043	17.7309 0.0043	0.0217 0.0068	0.0937 0.0042	0.0033 0.0039	0.0185 0.0050	0.0000 0.0080	0.0211 0.0068	27	1.6	1.2
5971314339012488832	0.40914 0.00013	2286.6709 0.0012	18.5141 0.0025	0.0025 0.0037	0.0937 0.0034	-0.0109 0.0034	0.0036 0.0031	0.0000 0.0035	-0.0019 0.0035	35	1.6	1.2
5867831598804630144	0.66770 0.00030	2190.5757 0.0025	18.6777 0.0031	0.0141 0.0045	0.0936 0.0045	0.0102 0.0041	0.0004 0.0043	0.0000 0.0042	-0.0028 0.0044	43	1.6	1.1
4116793738878178304	0.63592 0.00023	2453.6713 0.0015	18.0681 0.0019	-0.0100 0.0029	0.0936 0.0028	-0.0049 0.0027	0.0014 0.0026	0.0000 0.0028	0.0012 0.0029	56	1.6	1.2
1825488163123795328	0.337134 0.000076	2193.8147 0.0011	18.8592 0.0030	-0.0145 0.0050	0.0936 0.0059	-0.0152 0.0051	0.0020 0.0046	0.0000 0.0035	0.0038 0.0045	48	1.6	1.1
4043982227758966528	1.10801 0.00066	2352.9371 0.0050	18.2308 0.0037	0.0033 0.0057	0.0935 0.0055	0.0139 0.0050	-0.0029 0.0046	0.0000 0.0050	0.0099 0.0057	39	1.6	1.1
4363575893862498304	0.303803 0.000056	2328.88963 0.00069	17.3953 0.0019	-0.0181 0.0027	0.0935 0.0030	-0.0012 0.0026	-0.0013 0.0026	0.0000 0.0025	0.0054 0.0029	45	1.6	1.2
6026017752571334400	0.320724 0.000085	2300.6648 0.0012	18.6999 0.0035	-0.0237 0.0048	0.0935 0.0058	0.0001 0.0056	0.0051 0.0054	0.0000 0.0045	-0.0081 0.0051	42	1.6	1.1
4151366060896624256	0.69710 0.00037	2241.3239 0.0019	17.7912 0.0024	-0.0024 0.0039	0.0935 0.0029	0.0008 0.0026	-0.0033 0.0028	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0084 0.0028	28	1.6	1.2
4310698008860121216	0.75138 0.00044	2242.7163 0.0016	16.9948 0.0021	-0.0274 0.0034	0.0935 0.0034	-0.0103 0.0026	0.0068 0.0025	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0001 0.0026	31	1.6	1.2
4120578330962979456	0.47945 0.00016	2465.9817 0.0011	17.9132 0.0019	0.0270 0.0029	0.0934 0.0024	0.0086 0.0026	-0.0036 0.0026	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0012 0.0027	54	1.6	1.2
5943198864598128000	0.391194 0.000094	2272.87717 0.00079	17.6130 0.0016	-0.0087 0.0022	0.0933 0.0027	-0.0077 0.0026	-0.0006 0.0024	0.0000 0.0021	-0.0009 0.0024	39	1.6	1.2
2057341939546521472	0.76659 0.00042	2228.2136 0.0016	18.2265 0.0020	-0.0078 0.0025	0.0933 0.0030	0.0040 0.0024	0.0073 0.0032	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0123 0.0033	50	1.6	1.2
5994289008090288640	0.347696 0.000070	2044.6598 0.0017	18.2809 0.0044	0.0198 0.0060	0.0932 0.0066	0.0071 0.0059	0.0123 0.0064	0.0000 0.0059	-0.0002 0.0066	49	1.6	1.1
5881565705973807744	1.4167 0.0014	2149.0462 0.0034	17.3205 0.0022	0.0035 0.0033	0.0932 0.0029	0.0083 0.0027	-0.0032 0.0025	0.0000 0.0027	0.0023 0.0029	43	1.6	1.2

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
2059063774754650880	0.91320 0.00051	2218.5903 0.0038	19.0771 0.0038	0.0195 0.0047	0.0932 0.0057	0.0190 0.0049	0.0015 0.0060	0.0000 0.0049	-0.0075 0.0050	52	1.6	1.1
2168646566775705088	1.10239 0.00077	2213.8016 0.0026	17.3466 0.0021	-0.0117 0.0025	0.0931 0.0031	-0.0013 0.0029	0.0048 0.0034	0.0000 0.0026	0.0011 0.0028	41	1.6	1.1
5899729152678191488	0.380766 0.000096	2127.7119 0.0015	18.4759 0.0031	-0.0232 0.0040	0.0931 0.0049	0.0071 0.0043	0.0107 0.0050	0.0000 0.0043	-0.0033 0.0045	47	1.6	1.1
4067298574383612672	0.59294 0.00025	2383.6211 0.0017	17.8665 0.0025	0.0201 0.0040	0.0931 0.0035	0.0134 0.0032	-0.0061 0.0029	0.0000 0.0032	-0.0100 0.0036	43	1.6	1.1
5875031617582762624	0.55264 0.00024	2199.8224 0.0019	18.1768 0.0030	-0.0097 0.0041	0.0930 0.0035	0.0039 0.0036	0.0107 0.0044	0.0000 0.0044	0.0056 0.0043	45	1.6	1.1
5992628371912715392	1.01903 0.00047	2092.5844 0.0017	17.7464 0.0014	-0.0103 0.0022	0.0930 0.0021	0.0027 0.0020	0.0024 0.0018	0.0000 0.0018	0.0023 0.0019	66	1.6	1.2
4110726019578773120	0.61842 0.00027	2314.7957 0.0011	17.3155 0.0015	-0.0046 0.0023	0.0930 0.0023	-0.0068 0.0021	0.0000 0.0019	0.0000 0.0019	-0.0028 0.0021	49	1.6	1.2
4293810854615414784	0.68068 0.00034	2196.0645 0.0019	16.6854 0.0024	-0.0035 0.0033	0.0930 0.0034	0.0102 0.0029	0.0026 0.0035	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0036 0.0038	30	1.6	1.1
6008216968556546432	0.311063 0.000078	2079.19181 0.00093	17.9034 0.0029	0.0099 0.0051	0.0930 0.0053	-0.0090 0.0048	-0.0163 0.0036	0.0000 0.0033	0.0085 0.0036	41	1.6	1.1
2033474222172499968	0.99435 0.00070	2211.1893 0.0031	17.7999 0.0024	0.0143 0.0036	0.0930 0.0037	0.0044 0.0033	0.0130 0.0032	0.0000 0.0033	-0.0021 0.0037	48	1.6	1.1
4118634222571006976	0.48169 0.00015	2388.0678 0.0027	18.7444 0.0050	-0.0231 0.0063	0.0930 0.0075	-0.0116 0.0060	0.0057 0.0081	0.0000 0.0062	-0.0009 0.0079	43	1.6	1.0
5937544248141179008	0.49960 0.00017	2101.9102 0.0012	16.9530 0.0021	0.0150 0.0039	0.0929 0.0031	-0.0030 0.0024	0.0031 0.0020	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0024 0.0027	61	1.6	1.1
5971704833097543168	0.83264 0.00059	2274.0516 0.0026	18.3054 0.0027	0.0075 0.0034	0.0929 0.0039	0.0118 0.0038	-0.0091 0.0042	0.0000 0.0036	0.0051 0.0035	41	1.6	1.1
5972822177425474176	0.257090 0.000052	2290.11042 0.00049	16.9135 0.0017	-0.0089 0.0027	0.0929 0.0028	-0.0018 0.0022	-0.0042 0.0021	0.0000 0.0022	-0.0024 0.0029	27	1.6	1.1
5882261456319117440	0.339646 0.000094	2122.7734 0.0016	19.2242 0.0042	-0.0162 0.0065	0.0929 0.0057	0.0021 0.0057	0.0108 0.0052	0.0000 0.0058	0.0055 0.0055	46	1.6	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4163226698979126784	0.362717 0.000087	2386.19380 0.00075	18.5932 0.0017	-0.0115 0.0026	0.0928 0.0025	-0.0024 0.0024	0.0113 0.0022	0.0000 0.0023	0.0003 0.0024	51	1.6	1.1
4056840530856775168	0.74118 0.00026	2389.9054 0.0020	17.6444 0.0025	-0.0102 0.0034	0.0928 0.0032	0.0055 0.0028	-0.0056 0.0030	0.0000 0.0031	0.0034 0.0037	43	1.6	1.1
3020455473403312128	0.343936 0.000091	2306.98800 0.00087	17.6805 0.0024	-0.0219 0.0038	0.0928 0.0037	0.0024 0.0033	0.0083 0.0030	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0006 0.0033	33	1.6	1.1
4121045309772537600	0.72209 0.00040	2304.7961 0.0022	18.2669 0.0024	0.0150 0.0034	0.0927 0.0035	-0.0007 0.0032	-0.0040 0.0033	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0087 0.0036	39	1.6	1.1
4515710546088089344	1.3963 0.0013	2200.8673 0.0050	18.1871 0.0029	0.0279 0.0039	0.0926 0.0039	-0.0046 0.0043	0.0054 0.0042	0.0000 0.0042	0.0020 0.0038	53	1.6	1.1
5328547537954751232	1.04209 0.00068	2266.4639 0.0033	17.6644 0.0025	0.0113 0.0029	0.0926 0.0042	0.0050 0.0039	0.0072 0.0041	0.0000 0.0034	0.0088 0.0040	40	1.6	1.1
1826661857416121344	0.275488 0.000052	2127.9002 0.0011	18.2022 0.0034	-0.0178 0.0049	0.0926 0.0049	0.0069 0.0045	0.0050 0.0046	0.0000 0.0048	-0.0049 0.0052	54	1.6	1.1
5886930871683919232	0.58123 0.00021	2182.6683 0.0016	18.6587 0.0026	0.0134 0.0045	0.0925 0.0035	0.0023 0.0035	0.0035 0.0027	0.0000 0.0032	0.0084 0.0032	45	1.6	1.1
4044188931802966400	1.05793 0.00065	2427.6840 0.0025	17.9532 0.0020	0.0263 0.0028	0.0925 0.0027	0.0085 0.0033	-0.0209 0.0028	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0016 0.0025	56	1.6	1.1
4117616040406930688	0.67017 0.00026	2411.4473 0.0015	18.2388 0.0020	0.0075 0.0028	0.0925 0.0029	0.0025 0.0028	0.0039 0.0029	0.0000 0.0027	-0.0011 0.0029	47	1.6	1.1
5880978326225888000	0.99953 0.00064	2104.2498 0.0026	19.4702 0.0022	0.0174 0.0032	0.0925 0.0041	0.0046 0.0037	-0.0009 0.0037	0.0000 0.0027	-0.0040 0.0035	38	1.6	1.1
4118098966636199040	0.60001 0.00020	2416.1903 0.0013	17.9209 0.0020	0.0048 0.0028	0.0925 0.0031	-0.0092 0.0027	0.0027 0.0028	0.0000 0.0025	0.0064 0.0028	49	1.6	1.1
204842903200280064	0.37514 0.00012	2256.4455 0.0016	18.5973 0.0036	0.0301 0.0053	0.0925 0.0056	-0.0057 0.0063	-0.0052 0.0051	0.0000 0.0048	-0.0048 0.0045	46	1.6	1.1
5981814464556498304	0.84923 0.00045	2160.5058 0.0025	18.0740 0.0025	0.0121 0.0039	0.0925 0.0038	0.0014 0.0037	-0.0023 0.0032	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0019 0.0033	54	1.6	1.1
5972087703660023168	0.327445 0.000084	2286.11996 0.00090	18.2167 0.0022	-0.0084 0.0028	0.0925 0.0038	0.0004 0.0033	-0.0063 0.0036	0.0000 0.0026	0.0036 0.0032	55	1.6	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5827299275184119680	0.318691 0.000086	2170.42691 0.00089	18.1563 0.0023	-0.0267 0.0033	0.0924 0.0034	0.0036 0.0029	-0.0024 0.0033	0.0000 0.0033	-0.0010 0.0036	41	1.6	1.1
248990352345204736	0.283507 0.000070	2118.51277 0.00071	18.5419 0.0026	0.0114 0.0029	0.0924 0.0040	0.0111 0.0030	0.0160 0.0046	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0150 0.0041	35	1.5	1.1
447431550955645056	0.55883 0.00023	2162.64809 0.00099	17.0402 0.0015	0.0127 0.0020	0.0924 0.0019	-0.0002 0.0021	-0.0014 0.0019	0.0000 0.0021	-0.0068 0.0020	43	1.5	1.1
4320874749205944064	1.1894 0.0010	2152.7639 0.0051	18.0463 0.0037	-0.0169 0.0038	0.0923 0.0052	-0.0133 0.0044	0.0118 0.0062	0.0000 0.0042	0.0031 0.0041	36	1.5	1.1
4143871141177911424	0.50948 0.00024	2285.8313 0.0023	18.9006 0.0036	0.0179 0.0057	0.0922 0.0057	0.0117 0.0049	0.0114 0.0043	0.0000 0.0048	0.0108 0.0054	29	1.5	1.1
5941303409633668352	0.328864 0.000045	2098.37619 0.00073	17.8166 0.0021	-0.0137 0.0034	0.0922 0.0041	0.0014 0.0033	0.0165 0.0031	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0037 0.0033	66	1.5	1.1
2057701342412484864	0.43729 0.00013	2226.6597 0.0015	18.9683 0.0029	-0.0116 0.0041	0.0922 0.0041	-0.0083 0.0039	0.0058 0.0040	0.0000 0.0040	0.0064 0.0040	44	1.5	1.1
4093878473392045184	1.1766 0.0015	2277.7125 0.0028	17.1437 0.0022	0.0176 0.0036	0.0922 0.0031	0.0038 0.0031	0.0019 0.0025	0.0000 0.0027	0.0057 0.0027	29	1.5	1.1
2070452584917307392	0.78219 0.00054	2233.6351 0.0025	18.9005 0.0029	-0.0117 0.0035	0.0922 0.0042	-0.0058 0.0040	-0.0037 0.0045	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0014 0.0038	37	1.5	1.1
4119483904538549888	0.70011 0.00037	2279.5847 0.0020	18.9214 0.0024	-0.0107 0.0038	0.0922 0.0034	-0.0056 0.0032	-0.0078 0.0030	0.0000 0.0032	-0.0010 0.0029	34	1.5	1.1
4117177747570283648	0.68644 0.00028	2397.0437 0.0021	18.2191 0.0023	0.0265 0.0034	0.0922 0.0031	0.0003 0.0031	0.0039 0.0032	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0029 0.0035	47	1.5	1.1
2082840168254168704	0.309990 0.000057	2235.16632 0.00098	18.2965 0.0026	0.0182 0.0036	0.0921 0.0036	-0.0053 0.0033	-0.0053 0.0036	0.0000 0.0037	-0.0024 0.0039	42	1.5	1.1
2166489187524929152	0.66296 0.00034	2263.3103 0.0023	18.7785 0.0029	-0.0102 0.0042	0.0921 0.0038	0.0104 0.0040	-0.0112 0.0037	0.0000 0.0041	0.0088 0.0034	45	1.5	1.1
5834715545522454016	0.341319 0.000065	2165.5997 0.0012	18.1042 0.0029	0.0023 0.0042	0.0919 0.0043	0.0120 0.0042	0.0120 0.0039	0.0000 0.0041	-0.0061 0.0042	57	1.5	1.1
2030386553000124928	0.76120 0.00040	2234.9132 0.0022	18.7322 0.0024	-0.0095 0.0036	0.0919 0.0035	-0.0076 0.0036	0.0161 0.0032	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0021 0.0033	50	1.5	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5625094134724407296	0.56758 0.00016	2224.3793 0.0014	18.3033 0.0022	0.0102 0.0031	0.0919 0.0031	-0.0001 0.0030	-0.0043 0.0030	0.0000 0.0029	0.0121 0.0029	46	1.5	1.1
5980528413934936960	0.98810 0.00071	2334.1628 0.0025	18.4741 0.0020	0.0024 0.0031	0.0918 0.0032	0.0073 0.0031	0.0055 0.0028	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0057 0.0031	49	1.5	1.1
207660947209655552	0.34303 0.00011	2256.0130 0.0013	17.9652 0.0032	-0.0316 0.0058	0.0918 0.0049	-0.0060 0.0044	-0.0181 0.0034	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0012 0.0038	37	1.5	1.1
4143833001843654912	0.90265 0.00050	2275.5808 0.0020	16.6804 0.0018	0.0087 0.0023	0.0917 0.0028	0.0027 0.0023	0.0031 0.0027	0.0000 0.0023	0.0012 0.0027	30	1.5	1.1
5976765133512018048	0.77977 0.00058	2249.6368 0.0046	19.2559 0.0047	-0.0182 0.0059	0.0917 0.0067	-0.0050 0.0069	-0.0063 0.0071	0.0000 0.0065	-0.0042 0.0059	42	1.5	1.0
1825852380648525568	0.78382 0.00047	2142.4854 0.0030	19.3507 0.0032	0.0038 0.0045	0.0917 0.0047	-0.0151 0.0044	-0.0085 0.0046	0.0000 0.0044	0.0110 0.0042	43	1.5	1.1
5874498384473949952	0.327224 0.000058	2229.03668 0.00092	17.4565 0.0023	0.0139 0.0035	0.0917 0.0037	0.0006 0.0033	-0.0179 0.0031	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0003 0.0034	57	1.5	1.1
4119844368194081536	0.89974 0.00048	2443.3744 0.0022	18.2460 0.0020	0.0120 0.0030	0.0917 0.0032	-0.0032 0.0028	0.0006 0.0028	0.0000 0.0026	0.0008 0.0031	56	1.5	1.1
4049886948789883520	0.89627 0.00058	2247.2411 0.0020	16.8148 0.0019	0.0047 0.0023	0.0917 0.0029	0.0037 0.0027	-0.0024 0.0029	0.0000 0.0023	-0.0080 0.0027	27	1.5	1.1
5320873629683093632	0.315678 0.000085	2220.1434 0.0011	17.7923 0.0027	-0.0107 0.0037	0.0916 0.0036	-0.0047 0.0038	0.0005 0.0038	0.0000 0.0039	0.0105 0.0037	37	1.5	1.1
4117606965114089600	0.74470 0.00029	2481.2715 0.0014	17.7954 0.0015	-0.0059 0.0020	0.0916 0.0023	-0.0091 0.0021	0.0016 0.0023	0.0000 0.0021	-0.0008 0.0023	57	1.5	1.1
2167505033188323968	1.06422 0.00094	2213.7029 0.0046	18.3751 0.0043	0.0271 0.0037	0.0916 0.0058	0.0196 0.0046	0.0041 0.0080	0.0000 0.0047	-0.0068 0.0053	38	1.5	1.0
2064907060581325312	0.88490 0.00050	2246.4906 0.0030	18.5919 0.0027	0.0151 0.0037	0.0916 0.0037	0.0125 0.0039	0.0011 0.0039	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0077 0.0037	46	1.5	1.1
5963284055800046208	0.64241 0.00044	2260.0021 0.0018	18.2018 0.0026	0.0030 0.0035	0.0916 0.0041	0.0054 0.0036	-0.0120 0.0038	0.0000 0.0033	0.0002 0.0037	43	1.5	1.1
5961314860547542272	0.56659 0.00019	2442.4475 0.0027	18.3929 0.0041	0.0214 0.0068	0.0915 0.0059	0.0115 0.0058	-0.0016 0.0048	0.0000 0.0052	-0.0004 0.0053	44	1.5	1.0

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4041781997731010560	0.54160 0.00023	2453.7587 0.0018	17.8955 0.0026	-0.0382 0.0035	0.0915 0.0035	-0.0216 0.0035	0.0024 0.0039	0.0000 0.0038	0.0054 0.0037	47	1.5	1.1
5937640004367021056	0.65716 0.00034	2267.8089 0.0015	17.2796 0.0020	0.0104 0.0031	0.0915 0.0029	0.0007 0.0027	0.0041 0.0026	0.0000 0.0027	0.0014 0.0027	41	1.5	1.1
5941788874056868224	0.66697 0.00033	2188.1619 0.0017	18.0719 0.0024	-0.0183 0.0032	0.0915 0.0035	-0.0004 0.0032	0.0070 0.0033	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0046 0.0032	37	1.5	1.1
5988085121143687936	0.76055 0.00042	2088.7905 0.0019	17.4711 0.0021	-0.0100 0.0031	0.0915 0.0029	-0.0047 0.0027	-0.0056 0.0027	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0044 0.0030	45	1.5	1.1
276523566614691328	0.351595 0.000065	2162.45647 0.00078	18.2221 0.0019	-0.0136 0.0029	0.0914 0.0034	0.0025 0.0030	0.0095 0.0029	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0066 0.0028	74	1.5	1.1
5996899798450078336	0.33411 0.00012	2048.4372 0.0010	18.3829 0.0020	0.0092 0.0029	0.0914 0.0035	-0.0079 0.0034	-0.0055 0.0031	0.0000 0.0033	0.0004 0.0031	51	1.5	1.1
2021284349073934464	0.360199 0.000074	2247.96470 0.00084	18.6175 0.0019	-0.0143 0.0027	0.0914 0.0026	0.0012 0.0027	-0.0039 0.0026	0.0000 0.0028	0.0029 0.0026	86	1.5	1.1
2068602141207393536	0.79395 0.00041	2213.8988 0.0023	17.8619 0.0026	-0.0036 0.0038	0.0914 0.0038	-0.0047 0.0036	0.0186 0.0035	0.0000 0.0034	0.0010 0.0037	43	1.5	1.1
4111120125751883136	1.03307 0.00079	2336.5157 0.0020	17.4954 0.0015	-0.0077 0.0021	0.0913 0.0025	-0.0012 0.0021	0.0004 0.0022	0.0000 0.0019	0.0050 0.0022	59	1.5	1.1
4099704411943299584	0.45503 0.00012	2208.61771 0.00098	18.2109 0.0018	-0.0055 0.0027	0.0913 0.0029	-0.0086 0.0027	-0.0138 0.0025	0.0000 0.0024	-0.0002 0.0026	28	1.5	1.1
2070671800043522816	0.72265 0.00041	2211.5414 0.0017	18.4693 0.0019	0.0047 0.0028	0.0913 0.0027	0.0113 0.0028	-0.0185 0.0027	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0002 0.0028	48	1.5	1.1
4302041656898064000	0.270171 0.000065	2173.91683 0.00097	18.2411 0.0032	-0.0086 0.0041	0.0913 0.0043	-0.0029 0.0039	0.0165 0.0046	0.0000 0.0043	-0.0122 0.0049	39	1.5	1.0
247176849656507392	0.46842 0.00015	2139.23604 0.00083	17.4955 0.0015	0.0104 0.0021	0.0913 0.0022	-0.0033 0.0022	0.0055 0.0021	0.0000 0.0020	0.0015 0.0020	65	1.5	1.1
4312619645957182592	0.61736 0.00035	2228.1260 0.0019	17.6956 0.0023	-0.0117 0.0033	0.0912 0.0027	-0.0077 0.0033	-0.0032 0.0036	0.0000 0.0041	-0.0012 0.0038	27	1.5	1.1
4044125336065254784	0.392346 0.000082	2389.7711 0.0010	17.7688 0.0021	0.0015 0.0035	0.0912 0.0033	-0.0035 0.0029	-0.0128 0.0026	0.0000 0.0026	0.0026 0.0030	53	1.5	1.1

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
154974759483084800	0.328355 0.000089	2227.04151 0.00098	17.9959 0.0024	0.0114 0.0034	0.0911 0.0036	-0.0025 0.0032	-0.0037 0.0034	0.0000 0.0032	0.0004 0.0036	43	1.5	1.1
4057433962273137024	1.3856 0.0015	2395.0994 0.0036	17.4323 0.0021	-0.0302 0.0027	0.0911 0.0030	-0.0113 0.0026	-0.0044 0.0032	0.0000 0.0028	0.0045 0.0030	38	1.5	1.1
5900910715358995712	0.330491 0.000083	2073.81110 0.00082	18.2893 0.0021	0.0125 0.0028	0.0911 0.0036	0.0039 0.0034	0.0034 0.0035	0.0000 0.0026	-0.0059 0.0029	47	1.5	1.1
5971306058314604416	0.73353 0.00052	2252.1664 0.0025	18.0904 0.0027	-0.0072 0.0039	0.0911 0.0038	-0.0091 0.0035	-0.0035 0.0038	0.0000 0.0038	0.0069 0.0042	45	1.5	1.0
5863313671165798400	0.42933 0.00012	2250.1111 0.0012	19.2756 0.0024	-0.0553 0.0033	0.0910 0.0035	-0.0087 0.0032	0.0037 0.0033	0.0000 0.0032	0.0024 0.0034	51	1.5	1.1
5938179658413745408	0.38333 0.00012	2281.3821 0.0012	18.1852 0.0027	-0.0140 0.0042	0.0910 0.0044	-0.0054 0.0037	0.0117 0.0037	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0009 0.0042	43	1.5	1.0
251995150125170176	0.55580 0.00024	2107.9947 0.0018	19.2141 0.0027	0.0221 0.0042	0.0910 0.0041	0.0086 0.0041	-0.0039 0.0035	0.0000 0.0036	0.0015 0.0037	44	1.5	1.0
5307187600455149440	0.48955 0.00013	2088.1761 0.0014	18.3497 0.0022	0.0392 0.0037	0.0910 0.0035	0.0018 0.0031	-0.0218 0.0026	0.0000 0.0027	0.0032 0.0029	51	1.5	1.1
5972041597240517888	0.90025 0.00065	2264.2455 0.0021	17.8021 0.0019	-0.0090 0.0025	0.0910 0.0025	-0.0036 0.0023	-0.0045 0.0027	0.0000 0.0026	0.0018 0.0028	48	1.5	1.1
5972962197660553344	0.62191 0.00029	2300.5718 0.0020	18.8714 0.0025	-0.0112 0.0035	0.0909 0.0035	-0.0048 0.0038	0.0161 0.0035	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0063 0.0033	69	1.5	1.0
183793676507073536	0.80890 0.00055	2255.7543 0.0021	17.8467 0.0024	0.0097 0.0036	0.0909 0.0032	0.0114 0.0026	-0.0004 0.0029	0.0000 0.0031	0.0020 0.0033	29	1.5	1.1
5834273546240620160	0.328038 0.000069	2172.67542 0.00073	17.0265 0.0019	-0.0015 0.0030	0.0909 0.0029	-0.0020 0.0025	0.0074 0.0022	0.0000 0.0023	0.0000 0.0025	48	1.5	1.1
2075326032771354752	0.267476 0.000054	2184.59330 0.00095	18.5656 0.0030	-0.0132 0.0043	0.0908 0.0043	-0.0028 0.0039	-0.0138 0.0041	0.0000 0.0040	0.0002 0.0044	48	1.4	1.0
5330205116149118208	0.54348 0.00019	2203.8449 0.0022	19.1236 0.0034	-0.0083 0.0050	0.0908 0.0051	0.0067 0.0049	0.0199 0.0046	0.0000 0.0046	0.0080 0.0049	40	1.4	1.0
5977757030454814848	0.359105 0.000094	2284.5927 0.0011	18.4917 0.0030	-0.0035 0.0049	0.0908 0.0051	0.0099 0.0050	-0.0015 0.0039	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0110 0.0040	46	1.4	1.0

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
4515508300374125056	0.368973 0.000084	2153.6964 0.0013	18.2387 0.0028	-0.0092 0.0042	0.0907 0.0042	-0.0011 0.0043	-0.0146 0.0039	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0050 0.0039	39	1.4	1.0
4111214610668581376	0.50810 0.00019	2308.7655 0.0019	18.3752 0.0031	0.0129 0.0046	0.0907 0.0049	-0.0110 0.0044	-0.0126 0.0047	0.0000 0.0045	0.0046 0.0049	43	1.4	1.0
4281707976043168384	0.57959 0.00028	2105.6485 0.0019	18.0342 0.0027	-0.0180 0.0034	0.0907 0.0035	-0.0077 0.0034	0.0075 0.0042	0.0000 0.0038	-0.0068 0.0039	43	1.4	1.0
4120093240073972864	0.52718 0.00017	2378.9015 0.0016	18.8404 0.0026	0.0031 0.0041	0.0907 0.0037	0.0120 0.0038	-0.0063 0.0031	0.0000 0.0036	-0.0004 0.0034	45	1.4	1.0
5833662969298401024	0.37362 0.00011	2197.14520 0.00091	17.6827 0.0019	0.0067 0.0030	0.0906 0.0031	-0.0039 0.0025	-0.0054 0.0025	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0019 0.0033	48	1.4	1.0
5847314166394061184	0.258907 0.000050	2194.04619 0.00085	18.5408 0.0027	0.0094 0.0039	0.0906 0.0036	0.0034 0.0038	-0.0265 0.0035	0.0000 0.0037	0.0029 0.0034	47	1.4	1.0
2056187834598367232	0.57763 0.00023	2233.9778 0.0011	17.8711 0.0015	-0.0036 0.0021	0.0906 0.0023	0.0025 0.0018	-0.0024 0.0022	0.0000 0.0021	0.0110 0.0025	42	1.4	1.1
4506469700652006656	0.74840 0.00055	2185.7816 0.0017	16.9831 0.0020	-0.0192 0.0028	0.0905 0.0027	-0.0104 0.0026	-0.0021 0.0025	0.0000 0.0027	-0.0037 0.0026	29	1.4	1.0
5836453323656146048	0.46730 0.00016	2180.43051 0.00099	17.7597 0.0017	-0.0126 0.0028	0.0905 0.0025	-0.0019 0.0027	-0.0007 0.0020	0.0000 0.0023	-0.0056 0.0022	59	1.4	1.1
5525928837412826624	0.40729 0.00012	2210.7510 0.0021	19.3407 0.0039	0.0090 0.0062	0.0905 0.0049	0.0038 0.0045	0.0148 0.0049	0.0000 0.0059	0.0007 0.0056	45	1.4	1.0
5884915539898670464	1.03953 0.00086	2190.6752 0.0037	18.0283 0.0028	0.0229 0.0039	0.0904 0.0038	0.0167 0.0040	-0.0068 0.0040	0.0000 0.0042	0.0070 0.0038	41	1.4	1.0
4322097779775468800	0.355248 0.000082	2181.27068 0.00070	17.9007 0.0017	0.0072 0.0024	0.0904 0.0026	0.0040 0.0026	0.0045 0.0024	0.0000 0.0022	0.0012 0.0023	39	1.4	1.0
4111720081094185600	0.74586 0.00046	2320.0609 0.0015	18.2949 0.0017	-0.0120 0.0021	0.0904 0.0023	-0.0066 0.0020	-0.0030 0.0024	0.0000 0.0023	-0.0033 0.0026	52	1.4	1.0
5993175653779697408	0.343801 0.000071	2262.74255 0.00098	18.5579 0.0023	0.0104 0.0036	0.0904 0.0040	0.0065 0.0038	-0.0196 0.0032	0.0000 0.0031	0.0026 0.0034	55	1.4	1.0
4340539514648010368	0.250363 0.000052	2172.5099 0.0014	18.3897 0.0056	-0.0065 0.0053	0.0903 0.0041	-0.0033 0.0049	0.0163 0.0056	0.0000 0.0062	0.0085 0.0063	49	1.4	1.0

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{-1\sigma}$
5887458809069673344	0.59334 0.00028	2144.9339 0.0020	18.8501 0.0027	0.0157 0.0037	0.0903 0.0037	0.0012 0.0041	-0.0010 0.0037	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0006 0.0038	41	1.4	1.0
3403528932292557952	0.52689 0.00018	2393.4995 0.0017	18.3607 0.0026	0.0165 0.0037	0.0903 0.0040	-0.0053 0.0030	-0.0077 0.0037	0.0000 0.0032	0.0068 0.0042	43	1.4	1.0
5980205947768977280	0.68675 0.00038	2331.0451 0.0011	17.4642 0.0014	-0.0035 0.0020	0.0902 0.0022	0.0059 0.0019	-0.0005 0.0021	0.0000 0.0018	0.0037 0.0021	34	1.4	1.0
6019891479940114944	0.58280 0.00028	2321.5005 0.0017	18.4539 0.0023	0.0080 0.0034	0.0902 0.0035	0.0102 0.0029	0.0034 0.0032	0.0000 0.0031	-0.0026 0.0037	49	1.4	1.0
251739234495031936	0.51267 0.00021	2111.6414 0.0012	18.0559 0.0017	-0.0092 0.0025	0.0902 0.0021	0.0033 0.0026	-0.0047 0.0022	0.0000 0.0026	0.0031 0.0021	46	1.4	1.0
4117363908727669760	0.79902 0.00033	2404.7088 0.0029	18.6146 0.0031	-0.0190 0.0043	0.0902 0.0043	0.0016 0.0041	0.0068 0.0041	0.0000 0.0039	0.0065 0.0038	43	1.4	1.0
5930627907700568320	0.322787 0.000068	2193.15833 0.00083	17.6523 0.0018	0.0044 0.0027	0.0902 0.0033	0.0049 0.0030	-0.0094 0.0029	0.0000 0.0025	0.0006 0.0028	52	1.4	1.0
4118863500745320064	1.11020 0.00089	2400.7877 0.0028	17.6203 0.0018	-0.0231 0.0028	0.0902 0.0027	-0.0049 0.0025	0.0012 0.0025	0.0000 0.0026	0.0062 0.0027	42	1.4	1.0
5983948071186821376	0.96239 0.00063	2094.2196 0.0020	17.6300 0.0018	0.0119 0.0027	0.0901 0.0031	-0.0036 0.0028	0.0050 0.0027	0.0000 0.0023	0.0005 0.0027	60	1.4	1.0
2034671732104144000	0.283357 0.000057	2210.58085 0.00056	17.9951 0.0018	0.0197 0.0027	0.0901 0.0029	0.0029 0.0026	0.0042 0.0021	0.0000 0.0022	-0.0008 0.0025	50	1.4	1.0
5891711758737858176	1.00313 0.00045	2185.1453 0.0028	17.9852 0.0024	0.0087 0.0032	0.0901 0.0039	0.0150 0.0033	-0.0002 0.0038	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0025 0.0037	59	1.4	1.0
4067808571662706688	0.60752 0.00026	2410.2267 0.0013	16.9705 0.0021	-0.0050 0.0025	0.0901 0.0032	0.0015 0.0026	0.0109 0.0034	0.0000 0.0025	0.0004 0.0032	39	1.4	1.0
5932862664994144128	0.55352 0.00025	2197.1331 0.0014	18.3145 0.0021	0.0129 0.0029	0.0900 0.0030	-0.0034 0.0029	0.0053 0.0030	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0016 0.0030	58	1.4	1.0
5875909886869867008	0.75001 0.00042	2225.8778 0.0026	18.2061 0.0031	0.0152 0.0037	0.0898 0.0035	-0.0008 0.0042	-0.0069 0.0036	0.0000 0.0039	-0.0050 0.0037	43	1.4	1.0
4057416129538784640	0.397563 0.000092	2377.0960 0.0012	18.2611 0.0025	0.0153 0.0039	0.0898 0.0034	-0.0063 0.0041	0.0047 0.0033	0.0000 0.0034	-0.0027 0.0028	40	1.4	1.0

Table S1: Continued.

<i>Gaia</i> DR3	P P_{err} [day]	T_0 $T_{0,\text{err}}$ BJD – 2455197.5	$\bar{G}$ $\bar{G}_{\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1c} $a_{1c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2c} $a_{2c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3c} $a_{3c,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{1s} $a_{1s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{2s} $a_{2s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	a_{3s} $a_{3s,\text{err}}$ [mag]	N	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}$	$\hat{q}_{\text{min}}^{1\sigma}$
5870863094153430144	0.82485 0.00047	2194.6947 0.0019	17.0445 0.0019	-0.0248 0.0028	0.0898 0.0028	-0.0057 0.0024	0.0054 0.0026	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0015 0.0031	47	1.4	1.0
5951023328613748224	0.65922 0.00038	2239.6565 0.0017	17.5573 0.0021	0.0143 0.0032	0.0897 0.0031	0.0023 0.0030	0.0011 0.0027	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0021 0.0028	37	1.4	1.0
1827494570016143232	0.64416 0.00033	2169.3121 0.0015	18.4896 0.0019	-0.0052 0.0027	0.0897 0.0026	0.0020 0.0026	-0.0107 0.0027	0.0000 0.0028	-0.0019 0.0026	39	1.4	1.0
4117020345704069760	1.11632 0.00077	2416.6376 0.0032	18.3325 0.0022	-0.0139 0.0031	0.0896 0.0032	-0.0101 0.0032	0.0022 0.0031	0.0000 0.0033	0.0006 0.0034	41	1.4	1.0
4303135774045677952	0.68752 0.00033	2112.4090 0.0018	17.8086 0.0021	-0.0059 0.0027	0.0895 0.0027	-0.0040 0.0025	-0.0023 0.0031	0.0000 0.0029	-0.0099 0.0028	41	1.4	1.0
5516255540272479744	0.67690 0.00032	2217.3634 0.0015	17.8357 0.0019	0.0079 0.0028	0.0894 0.0028	-0.0002 0.0026	0.0038 0.0025	0.0000 0.0024	0.0017 0.0025	41	1.4	1.0
4121520023917835904	0.62882 0.00023	2459.3046 0.0014	17.9100 0.0018	0.0121 0.0025	0.0893 0.0025	0.0068 0.0025	0.0002 0.0024	0.0000 0.0025	-0.0002 0.0026	53	1.4	1.0

Table S1: Continued.